

Camiguin Island Adventure

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Abstract

The presence of cultural awareness and engagement in games promotes a positive attitude towards different multicultural issues. However, this is not evident among most of virtual reality games available on the market. The game developed provides entertainment and education through the immersive virtual promoting local culture. This game aimed on Camiguin island, an island in the southern part of the Philippines. The main character of this game is a young girl named Maya who must collect items, interact with the NPC (Non-Player Characters) and learn about the history of Camiguin. The environment of this game was developed based on the simulation of the island's geographical features and cultural aspects mapped in a 3D virtual reality using the Unity 3D platform.

Keywords: game, Camiguin, Unity 3D

1-Introduction

The sophistication of virtual environments has become one of the major keys to the development of games. The integration of a virtual environment in games or simply called virtual reality or VR doesn't only allow users to interact and simulate real-world scenarios but also helps users solve real-world problems. Nowadays, games do not only provide entertainment but also learning, particularly in promoting cultural awareness and engagement. The promotion of cultural awareness creates a positive impact on the users' attitudes towards different multicultural issues. However, the promotion of cultural awareness in games is rare. As a result, this project aimed to develop a game that doesn't only provide entertainment but also cultural awareness and engagement.

A game with a happy atmosphere combining some competition strands always focusing on cooperation and trying to diminish the frustration and delivering a positive attitude – all these characteristics can be delivered by aiming the development centered in user capabilities, mitigating monotonous activities or tasks, simplifying the interaction, and immersing the user in an environment with encouraging music, sound effects, visual effects, and motivating dialogs.

The game was set on Camiguin island in the southern part of the Philippines. As an archipelago, the Philippines offer a very diverse culture, and the island of Camiguin provides a unique culture on its own. The island is also a famous tourist destination for local and international travelers. However, despite its popularity, little is known about Camiguin, especially its culture and tradition. Tourists who have visited the island discovered the island from friends as the region wherein Camiguin is situated is considered a high-risk area in many Western countries. So, numerous travel advisories were promoted even though Camiguin is thousand miles away from the small war-torn region of the southern part of the Philippines. So, the use of Camiguin as the location of the developed game will provide a positive attitude towards the island's culture and geography through virtual reality.

This game pioneers the promotion of the island of Camiguin and its culture. This can be very significant in the development of future virtual reality, especially in the promotion of cultural awareness of a particular area.

2-Development

The first phase of the development includes: planning the game script, defining the type of game and writing the goals and the environment together with research that collected information about the island population, cultural aspects, and natural resources. The game goals and activities were also based on cultural features of the island and the country as well.

Geographical features

The environment is based on the geographical features of Camiguin Island, Philippines. The Island was fully digitalized by mapping its height (see Figure 1), contour and texture based on the aerial and satellite images provided by OpenStreetMaps (see Figure 2). The flora in the island is mainly tropical with some specific features which were not fully digitized, but partially represented to mimic the experience of being inside the real island.

Figure 1 - OpenStreetMap map of Camiguin

Extraction of the altitude map (altimetry) – each pixel intensity represents the height in an adjusted scale from the minimum height to the maximum height.

Figure 2 - Pixel intensity altitude map (left) and the texture map (right)

Figure 3 - 3D map generated with Unity 3D Terrain Toolbox

Later, the size and heights were adjusted to make the map walkable by the player. This was done because the real altitude of the island would make the experience of walking impossible in some

places due the steepness. A low deep-water area was added just to make the player able to navigate to other small islands so this way the experience was simplified by not adding swimming and diving capabilities to the character – he/she can just walk on the water (see Figure 3).

Flora

Coconut trees are common trees present in Camiguin. In this environment, these trees are very present, and several types were placed in the terrain trying to be close as possible to the real island (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Real picture from Camiguin trees (left) and the 3D representation of these trees

Scenario

The scenario is culturally based on the specificities of the Philippines, trying to express the architecture and lifestyle of the population by adding some 3D models close to the real world in a way that the user can feel immersed in the atmosphere of this tropical island. Bahay Kubo or Payag in Cebuano is one of the iconic houses found in the Philippines (see Figure 6) which was used as an inspiration to build the main character house (Maya's Balay – Maya's House – see Figure 5) as well as the houses in several areas inside the island.

Figure 5 - Bahay Kubo in Filipino or payag in Cebuano – minimalist “Cube House” and typical filipino house.

Figure 6 - Bahay Kubo/Payag in the Philippines. Credits: BHD

Bangka is a typical boat found in the Philippines (see Figure 7) and it has an important effect in the user experience because it is quite present in the sea and heavily linked to the sea culture in the Philippines.

Figure 7 - Typical Boat – called “Bangka” (left) and its 3D representation (right).
Credits: CURTIS PETER VAN GORDER

Gameplay

Starting at Maya's Balay (Maya's house), the player must collect seven sun figures distributed across several points of interest of the island. These figures are present in the country's national flag.

The points of interest are:

- Benoni Port – starting point
- Binangawan Falls
- Mount Mambajao
- Taguines Lagoon
- Guinsiliban
- Sagay
- Catarman
- Hibok-Hibok Volcano
- Mambajao

To go to a specific point of interest the user will be able to check how far the closest one is from the current location displayed in the screen at the right top corner (check “Closest Place” in the Figure 8) – walking can be very slow so the user can also run, which has a cost of energy. The figure 8 shows at the top left corner the number of collected sun figure (zero in this case), at the top right corner the closest place in a straight line, at the bottom left the energy bar (in this case 19), and at the bottom right the total score (in this case zero).

Figure 8 - Player at the starting point - Benoni Port.

To collect energy the character must “consume” food on the floor. The energy level drops from time to time and faster when the user runs.

By reaching zero level of energy the character is transported to a “dream mode” with the goal of gain some energy back – during this mode the scene is at night and there are just some lights spread around and enemies following the character with the goal of decrease the energy.

Figure 9 - Player at the "dream mode"

In this case the user must run and avoid the enemies (called Wak-Wak) and reach home as soon as possible. These enemies might appear during the normal mode after the player collects a sun figure.

HUD

The fixed panel visible during the game play, known as HUD (Heads-up Display), contains information about the current score, energy level, number of items collected, and distance from the user position to the closest goal – a place where a sun figure might be.

Menus

When the user enters the game, the main menu is loaded with three options: Single Player, Credits and Exit. By hitting single player, a new scene is loaded, and the game starts with a popup screen containing some initial instructions – for further instructions about the game play and how to operate the character the user must access the Help menu.

In the help menu, there are instructions about the goal of the game and an explanation about the HUD information, as well as the key bindings for each type of possible interactions the user can experience, including how to move, jump, collect items and so on.

At any time during the game the user can hit the ESC (escape key) and access the game menu with the options of Resume the game, return back home (be transferred from the current location to the initial spawn area), access the settings or simply exit the game.

Persistence

Information like score, sun figures collected, and energy levels are persisted, meaning that the player can always return to game, and this information will be preserved and reloaded every time the game is accessed. The user will always be spawn in the initial area – called Home- regardless of its last position inside the island before closing the window or reloading the page.

The persistence is done using PlayerPrefs class provided by Unity 3D.

Unity 3D project organization

This project was designed using Unity 3D platform version 2020.3.31f1 with the Standard Assets installed plus libraries for trees, rain effect, music, sky box, water, and roads.

All custom scripts, prefabs, sprites and imported 3D models from different marketplaces are placed on CamiguinAssets folder (see Figure 10).

Figure 10 - Assets folder used store the objects used on this project

The main script is GameManager.cs responsible to control the connection between the player and the options available, places to collect figures and energy prefabs available.

The connection between the player and the options is done by simply holding the methods to display/hide menus when the player interacts with the game menu.

The spawning of energy items is also done by this script, which has the responsibility of generating the energy items on the fly as the user walks.

PlayerInventory.cs is the script holding the data and operations related with the collected items, score, and energy levels. As the user collects (hits) an energy item (or food item) the collider triggers an event captured by the EnergyCollectable.cs script attached to the energy item, if the collider which triggered this event is has a PlayerInventory.cs component, a method is called on PlayerInventory to increase the energy. The logic is implemented for the enemies but to decrease the energy. For the sun figures, the script processing the collider trigger is MainCollectable.cs.

Avatars

The main character and the NPCs were developed using the MakeHuman tool. The avatars were created considering the facial features, clothing, and body type of Filipinos (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Maya's avatar being edit in the MakeHuman tool

3D models

Churches are very present in the Philippines from several denominations, especially catholic. To represent their religion matrix, trying to be as democratic as possible, it was decided not to create or use 3D models with any specific religion, instead it was opted to use or create 3D models for churches without crosses or any religious symbols this way representing all types of faith equally. Two models were created for churches using the SketchUp Make 2017 tool (see Figure 12).

Figure 12 - 3D church model created in the SketchUp Make 2017

Scenes

MenuScreen – initial screen – first one to be displayed to the user.

This scene has no Sky box nor lighting, it is just a canvas presenting the initial menu with options to Play the game, open the credits/collaborations menu and exit the game.

DayScene – this is the main scene, where the player must collect the figures to finish the game.

This scene has a Sky box (Epic_BlueSunset Equirect provided by All Sky Free package), a directional light, canvas with menus and HUD, terrain with the whole map of the island, road network around the terrain, NPCs Celia, Rina and Carlos, player, points of interest, water, and background music.

Dream – this an intermediary scene displayed when the player energy level reaches zero, so it can be replenished by running back home from a specific place on the map.

This scene has a Sky box (Cold Night), no directional light and only some spotlights to guide the user back home. The terrain is the same as the Day Scene and NPC Celia is the only one available (it is also the enemy). The rain script provided by RainMaker package is active in this scene as well as an eerie music background giving an as scary as it can be atmosphere.

GameEnd – final screen – displayed after the user captures all 7 sun figures.

This scene has no Sky box nor lighting, it is just a canvas presenting the credits and contributions to the project.

3-Conclusion

This game was created with the intent of promoting the Camiguin Island and sharing with other some aspects of the culture and environment of this natural beauty. The core functionalities of the game were implemented, and they met most of the expectations for a virtual reality solution by providing an immersive experience to the user, mostly by inciting their curiosity, exciting their senses, teaching about the island in an educational and fun manner. Due this project limited time and scope some functionalities proposed are still open to be implemented or improved, as described below:

- Implement dialog interaction with NPCs
- Improve performance for WEBGL
- Add more options in the settings menu
- Implement multiplayer environment
- Add a scoreboard
- Improve the scene details
- Refactor the project to improve reuse and modularization.
- Add Bisaya language internalization
- Improve content
- Create a marketplace for NFTs inside the game (mostly digital art/photographs related to the island)

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